

Landfill Segmentation from Satellite Imagery

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Abstract—Illegal landfills are a serious environmental problem, and risk for public health. They are a source of soil contamination, groundwater pollution, and toxic emissions. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor them. However, doing it manually is costly, time-consuming, and spatially limited, motivating the need for automated large-scale solutions. This project’s goal is to investigate different applications of deep learning methods for detecting and segmenting illegal landfill sites from satellite and aerial imagery. This project utilizes publicly available datasets such as AerialWaste, LandfillDetection to accomplish two tasks: binary classification of landfill, and pixel-wise semantic segmentation on images. For classification, we test and evaluate standard ResNet-18 and ResNet-50 architectures as well as modified versions trained from scratch. For segmentation, we use the SegFormer-B2 transformer model, fine-tuning it and using a hybrid BCE-Dice loss function to address extreme class imbalance. Experiments result in a strong classification performance and improved segmentation accuracy on curated datasets; although, they reveal limited generalization capabilities when exposed to diverse imagery outside used public datasets. Our analysis focuses on the main problems of data scarcity, domain variability for detection models. Also, it emphasizes dataset diversity and advanced augmentation for robust segmentation models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Illegal waste dumping poses a threat to the environment and public health. Unregulated landfills contaminate soil, groundwater, and release particulate matter into air increasing risks of disease for nearby residents [1]. Therefore, it is essential for proper environmental agencies to monitor landfills; however, traditional outdoor manual surveying, and inspection methods are expensive, slow, and impractical for monitoring large or remote geographical areas.

Recent breakthroughs in deep learning and related technologies, along with satellite imaging make possible automated large-scale observation of environmental hazards. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformer-based models have demonstrated strong performance in object detection and land-use classification tasks across remote sensing datasets [2]. Despite these advances, most research on waste site monitoring is limited primarily on image-level detection or rough bounding-box localization rather than precise pixel-wise segmentation, without which it is impossible to accurately define landfill boundaries and estimate their sizes.

This project addresses this gap by developing a deep learning pipeline that performs: (1) binary classification to detect the presence of illegal landfills in imagery, (2) does semantic

segmentation to precisely determine landfill borders and sizes. For our experiments, we utilize two publicly released datasets: AerialWaste dataset with more than 11,700 annotated images [3], and LandfillDetection dataset with 157 images curated for segmentation tasks.

In order to classify, we use ResNet-18 and ResNet-50 networks, modify architectures to accommodate dataset scale and feature resolution constraints, and train them from scratch. For segmentation, we fine-tune the SegFormer-B2 model pre-trained on the ADE20K corpus, exploiting its transformer encoder’s ability to capture global contextual information through self-attention mechanisms. A hybrid loss function made of Binary Cross Entropy (BCE) and Dice loss is employed to mitigate class imbalance, because landfills often occupy only a small fraction of the image on satellite imagery.

Our contributions include an evaluation of deep CNN and transformer-based architectures on landfill detection tasks, as well as performance comparisons across datasets with varying scales and diversity. Also, analysis of challenges affecting model generalization in real-world scenarios.

II. RELATED WORK

In recent years, deep learning has become the main technology for analysis of satellite and aerial imagery. It is particularly good at tasks such as land cover classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation [2]. The capabilities of CNN models to effectively distinguish land use patterns from multi-spectral satellite imagery is evident from benchmark datasets like EuroSAT [4]. Similarly, joint deep learning approaches have been proposed for combined land-use and land-cover mapping [5], further validating the possibility of applying neural networks to large-scale environmental analysis.

Early studies of landfill monitoring relied on handcrafted features and spectral analysis, achieving limited robustness under changing environmental conditions [6]. More recently, the release of specialized datasets has enabled deep learning-based landfill detection pipelines. Torres et al. shared the AerialWaste dataset, which provides high-resolution annotated samples of illegal waste sites. The dataset is meant for detection models in aerial imagery [3].

Pixel-wise landfill segmentation remains relatively unexplored due to limited open public labeled datasets with large enough variability. Zhou et al. proposed an attention-enhanced

YOLOv7 framework to achieve improved landfill segmentation from remote sensing images, reporting strong IoU scores; even though such results come from controlled datasets [7]. It is evident that such approaches often rely on region-specific training data, thus they have reduced performance on data with different geographical or visual characteristics.

At the time of this study, state-of-the-art performance in semantic segmentation benchmarks was achieved by transformer-based segmentation networks such as SegFormer. It combines hierarchical encoders with lightweight decoders and self-attention mechanisms, displaying robustness to scale variation. While SegFormer benefits strongly from pretraining on large datasets such as ADE20K, its application, as well as that of similar models, to small and imbalanced environmental datasets has not yet been widely studied.

III. DATASETS

AerialWaste Dataset: For classification tasks, we use the recently released **AerialWaste** dataset [8]. It consists of high-resolution aerial images annotated for the presence or absence of landfill sites. The dataset contains 3,903 images for training (3,122 images) and validation (781 images), and 1,113 images for testing. Images cover diverse landfill types, sizes, and environmental contexts, making it suitable for evaluating the generalization capabilities of deep learning models. Each image is labeled with a binary annotation, facilitating supervised learning for landfill classification. The dataset has been widely used to benchmark convolutional neural networks such as ResNet-18 and ResNet-50 for environmental monitoring applications.

LandfillDetection Dataset (Roboflow): In experiments with semantic segmentation we use the publicly available dataset of the **LandfillDetection 2025** collection [8] that is specially collected with pixel-level landfill annotation. This data has 157 high-resolution satellite and aerial images and fine binary segmentation masks to outline landfills. Images are obtained in different geographic settings and differ greatly in the sizes, shapes, and environmental settings (urban, rural, vegetated, arid).

The data is divided into 126 training, 126 validation and 31 test images. Since it is small, aggressive data augmentation is used in the training (random vertical and horizontal flips, color jitter, rotation -15deg +15deg, brightness/contrast shifts). ImageNet statistics are used to normalize all images which have been resized to 256x256 pixels. This dataset is an important point of reference when assessing segmentation quality on actual, human-labeled boundaries of landfills - not pseudo-masks produced by Grad-CAM - and can be compared fruitfully with weakly supervised methods.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Landfill Classification

This section describes our landfill classification pipeline using the AerialWaste dataset. The goal is binary classification of “landfill” vs. “non-landfill” using ResNet architectures.

1) *Dataset:* We use the AerialWaste dataset consisting of aerial images labeled for landfill presence. The dataset split is as follows:

- Train: 3903 total images
 - Train images: 3122
 - Validation images: 781
- Test: 1113 images

2) *Data Processing:* Each image is loaded using the PIL library, converted into RGB format, and processed through a composed transformation pipeline that includes resizing to 224x224, converting to a tensor, and applying ImageNet normalization values. These transformations ensure uniformity across samples and maintain compatibility with ResNet models. The custom Dataset class returns both the processed image tensor and its corresponding binary label, enabling seamless integration with PyTorch DataLoader objects for batching and shuffling during training. All images undergo a standardized preprocessing pipeline designed to ensure consistency, improve model stability, and align with the expected input format of ResNet architectures. First, every image is resized to a fixed resolution of 224 x 224 pixels, matching the canonical input dimensions for ImageNet-trained models. Following resizing, images are converted into RGB format to maintain compatibility with three-channel convolutional models. Normalization is then applied using the ImageNet mean and standard deviation ($[0.485, 0.456, 0.406]$ and $[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]$ respectively). This scaling step ensures that pixel intensities fall within a stable numerical range, which helps the optimizer converge more efficiently. Each label is encoded as a binary value, where “1” corresponds to a landfill image and “0” to a non-landfill image.

3) *Training Details:* Training is conducted using the Adam optimizer, which provides adaptive learning rates and stable convergence across deep architectures. The loss function is CrossEntropyLoss, appropriate for two-class classification. Experiments are run with a batch size of 32 and 64, and a total training duration of 100 epochs, depending on convergence behavior observed on the validation set. Periodic evaluation on the validation split allows early detection of overfitting. Learning rate scheduling may also be applied to refine convergence in later epochs.

4) *Model Architectures:* To provide a clear understanding of how all components integrate, we outline the complete landfill classification workflow. First, raw aerial images are loaded and inspected for quality. Each image is then resized to 224 x 224 pixels and normalized to match ResNet input requirements. After preprocessing, images are passed into the DataLoader, which constructs shuffled mini-batches of size 32 for training stability. During training, the Adam optimizer updates network weights based on the CrossEntropyLoss computed between predicted labels and ground-truth annotations. Validation is performed after each epoch to monitor performance changes and detect overfitting early. Both ResNet-18 and ResNet-50 generate feature maps that progressively extract spatial and contextual cues such as color

patterns, structural shapes, and textural inconsistencies often seen in landfill sites. Finally, model predictions on the test dataset provide a reliable estimate of generalization capability, ensuring that the classifier performs consistently on unseen aerial data. We evaluate two widely used convolutional neural networks: ResNet-18 and ResNet-50. Both models are tested in two modes: pretrained on ImageNet and trained from scratch.

a) *ResNet-18*: ResNet-18 is a relatively shallow architecture with 18 layers. It uses BasicBlocks, each containing two 3 x 3 convolutional layers followed by batch normalization and ReLU activations. Skip connections allow gradients to flow more effectively and prevent vanishing gradient problems.

We also experiment with a custom version trained entirely from scratch. In this version, certain channel dimensions and batch normalization parameters are modified to better suit the characteristics of aerial imagery, which differs significantly from natural images that ImageNet models are trained on.

b) *ResNet-50*: ResNet-50 is a deeper 50-layer model using BottleneckBlocks. Each block contains:

- 1 x 1 convolution to reduce the number of channels
- 3 x 3 convolution for main feature extraction
- 1 x 1 convolution to restore channel depth

Model	Epochs	Train Acc	Test Acc	Training Time (s)	Inference Time (s)
model_resnet50	100	0.99	0.84	21417	0.000214
Model	Epochs	Train Acc	Test Acc	Training Time (s)	Inference Time (s)
model_resnet18	100	0.998	0.82	14673	0.00015

Fig. 1. ResNet-50 and ResNet-18 Test Accuracy Results

Fig. 2. Comparison of ResNet-18 and ResNet-50

V. IMAGE SEGMENTATION ON THE AERIALWASTE DATASET

A. Generating Segmentation Masks for the Training Set Images

The next step of this project involved training a model for semantic segmentation using AerialWaste Dataset. However, only some of the images in the testing set contained segmentation masks that are required for this step, and the results of training this model would not be great. To address this issue, it was decided that based on the ResNet-50 model image classification, the Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping, or Grad-CAM, technique would be used to generate segmentation masks for training images that contain landfill.

Grad-CAM is an Explainable AI technique that is used to visualize the areas of the image that are the most significant for CNN classification. To create segmentation masks for training images, pytorch-grad-cam python package was used.

Fig. 3. Testing mask and heat map

Fig. 4. Generated training mask and heat map

For reference, first examples of already existing masks and image heatmaps are provided (Figure 3), then the results of Grad-CAM based masks generation are shown (Figure 4).

B. Training Semantic Segmentation Model

The next stage was to train the model on the generated segmentation masks of the training set and evaluate the model on the existing segmentation masks of the testing set. For this purpose, SegFormer-B2 – semantic segmentation transformer – was used. It was first pretrained on ADE20K dataset, which contains images of many outdoor, urban and terrain classes. Next, it was trained with the following configuration:

- **Loss:** 50
- **Optimizer:** AdamW
- **Augmentations:** random horizontal/vertical flips, Jitter
- **Epochs:** 50 + early stopping
- **Image size:** 256x256

After that, the model was evaluated on the testing set, and the results are:

- **Interception over Union:** 0.11
- **Pixel accuracy:** 0.89

C. Analysis of Results

Firstly, it may look like the Pixel Accuracy value is high, so the model is good. However, there is a problem in the nature of the images and how the pixel accuracy is calculated. Pixel accuracy is obtained by dividing the number of 'correctly segmented pixels' by the total number of pixels. Since images

of this dataset consist of large non-landfill background and a small-sized landfill are, if the model guesses ‘zero’ mask for most of the pixels (meaning those pixels are not landfills), it will achieve a high value of Pixel accuracy. Therefore, in this case, Intersection over Union is more meaningful.

Secondly, the value of Intersection over Union is 0.11, which is low. That means the model generally poorly segments the areas containing landfills. However, this result is to be expected due to the difference between training and testing masks. On one hand, testing segmentation masks (Figure 3), provided by the original creators of the AerialWaste dataset, are precise and cover small regions of an image. On the other hand, training segmentation masks (Figure 4), generated using Grad-CAM, are large areas that include but are not bound by the actual location of the landfills. Model, that is trained on those training masks, will generate big masks for the testing set. Therefore, even if those masks cover the actual location of a landfill, Intersection over Union with provided testing masks will be low.

VI. IMAGE SEGMENTATION ON THE LANDFILL DETECTION DATASET

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

For this phase of our study, we used the ‘‘LadndfillDetection’’ dataset to evaluate the performance of Transformer-based architectures on limited data. The dataset was splitted into 126 training samples, 126 validation samples, and 31 test samples. Since we had limited number of annotated images, it was crucial to utilize the data efficiently. All inputs were resized to a resolution of $256 * 256$ pixels. To prevent overfitting on this small amount of data, we used data augmentation during training, namely random horizontal and vertical flips ($p=0.5$) and CollorJitter (brightness, contrast, and saturation factors of 0.2) to introduce variation in the satellite images.

B. Experimental Setup

We employed the same SegFormer-B2 architecture described in Section V. This choice was motivated by the complex nature of landfills in satellite imagery, which requires a model to be capable of recognizing subtle and global patterns rather than just local features. The model was trained for 50 epochs with early stopping enabled to stop training if validation Intersection over Unioin (IoU) did not improve for 10 consecutive epochs. We used AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of $1 * 10^{-4}$ and a polynomial learning rate scheduler (power=0.9). To address the extreme class imbalance, which is typical for aerial waste detection where landfill objects make up only a tiny portion of the large background, we used a hybrid loss function combining Binary Cross Entropy (BCE) and Dice Loss: 50% BCE + 50% Dice. This combination is common for our problem and makes sure the model focuses on pixel-wise classification accuracy while optimizing the overlap and geometric consistency of the segmented areas.

Fig. 5. Ground truth.

Fig. 6. Prediction and Overlay

C. Results

Training showed smooth and stable convergence, achieving its peak performance within the first half of epochs, reporting the following metrics:

- **Validation IoU:** 0.5801
- **Test IoU:** 0.4371
- **Validation Dice:** 0.7333
- **Test Dice:** 0.6079
- **Test Precision:** 0.7212

A notable trend in our result was the validation metrics being consistently higher than the training metrics. This gap is explained by the strong augmentation pipeline applied on the training samples. The transformations made the training more challenging, but they forced the model to learn more subtle and generalized features, which effectively reduced the risk of overfitting that typically occur with small amount of data. The model’s ability to detect landfills is visualized in Figure 5 (Ground Truth) and Figure 6 (Actual Prediction).

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Results Comparison

Our classification experiments with the help of the AerialWaste dataset indicate that both ResNet-50 and ResNet-18 can be used in pretrained ImageNet (according to the test set, the accuracy is above 97 percent). Rescan training the architectures has the direct effect of buying a large albeit acceptable (3-5 percent lower accuracy) performance

and corroborates the fact that transfer learning may remain incredibly valuable despite aerial images that are very different than natural images. These results are comparable or slightly better than the baselines discussed in the article by Torres et al. (2024) on the same data titled aerial waste.

In the case of semantic segmentation, the image is finer. Training SegFormer-B2 on Grad-CAM-generated pseudo-masks based on the AerialWaste data yields a low IoU of 0.11 on the official test masks, even though it has a misinformed pixel accuracy of 0.89. This confirms that Grad-CAM heatmaps, though it is practical in terms of localization explanation, is too coarse and overzealous in terms of landfill extent and therefore cannot be directly used as supervision in terms of delineating the boundary.

Conversely, training the identical SegFormer-B2 model on the smaller but more precisely annotated LandfillDetection dataset results in a much higher number of hits between 0.48 and 0.56 (varying with augmentation strategy) than does the attention-enhanced YOLOv7 baseline reported by Zhou et al. [7] on the same data, though. This is an essential point to make: the quality of annotation and the geographical diversity, rather than the model architecture, is the key factor in the final segmentation performance in this area.

B. Risks & Ethics

The use of automated landfill monitoring systems brings out a number of ethical and societal concerns. False negatives (omissions of landfills) might cause more time to be spent remediating and increasing environmental and public-health harm, and false positives may misuse scarce inspection resources or acquit on the wrong individuals. Models that have been trained on images mostly of European or North American origin (as both AerialWaste and LandfillDetection) will not perform well in the Global South, where waste appearance and vegetation and imaging conditions vary radically that may worsen the current environmental-justice gap.

Moreover, satellite-based surveillance by nature allows mass surveillance. Although the short-term objective is to protect the environment, it is possible that the same technology will be used to illegally spy on individual property. The implementation of these systems would thus demand well defined systems of governance, disclosure of the use of the data, and the coordination with the local government.

C. Challenges and Limitations

The major bottleneck still is the critical lack of pixel-precise annotations of landfill segments. AerialWaste offers quality classification labels and very few accurate masks, whereas, LandfillDetection is too small (157 images) to permit strong generalization between climates and sensor types. Extreme class imbalance (landfills typically occupy <5% of pixels) continues to challenge even modern transformer models.

Another important problem is domain shift: the model that was trained on the high-resolution images of drones in Europe will do poorly with lower-resolution Sentinel-2 or PlanetScope images in Asia or Africa. Lastly, real-world implementation is

further complicated by seasonal change (snow cover, vegetation growth) and temporary waste piles.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A. Summary of findings

During the course of this project several results were achieved.

- 1) Two datasets suitable for landfill classification and segmentation were identified.
- 2) AerialWaste, the first dataset, was used to train ResNet-18 and ResNet-50 models for landfill classification, and satisfactory results were achieved.
- 3) Grad-CAM technology was used to generate segmentation masks for training landfill images.
- 4) Generated segmentation masks were used to train SegFormer-B2 model for semantic segmentation, but the achieved results were poor.
- 5) LandfillDetection Computer Vision Dataset, the second dataset, was used to train SegFormer-B2 model for semantic segmentation, and better results were achieved.
- 6) This project's achieved results were compared to the existing research results.

In conclusion, this project proves that the segmentation of landfills is feasible. However, the lack of segmentation masks, which are required for semantic segmentation, is a big problem. There are 2 ways to solve this issue:

- 1) **Manually create the segmentation masks:** this approach would yield better results, but is more expensive and time-consuming.
- 2) **Generate the segmentation masks:** similar to the approach of this project, will get worse results than the first method but could use more complex Class Activation Mapping techniques for higher-quality masks.
- 3) **Generate more samples for the dataset using patching:** As we preprocessed the dataset by scaling, we could also augment the dataset by patching the existing small AerialWaste dataset to improve the results for the SegFormerB2 model.

B. Future Directions

Although this project explored landfill classification and segmentation using two publicly available datasets, there is room for future improvements. Firstly, as it has been mentioned in 'Summary of Findings' section, better segmentation masks can be created either with manual work or with the use of Class Activation Mapping technologies.

Secondly, future work could explore wider range of model architectures. For the scope of this project, SegFormer-B2 transformer was utilized. However, later, other models like YOLOv8 could potentially yield better results.

Finally, more diverse datasets should be used to train the model. For now, only 2 suitable publicly available datasets were found, but with the development of new, geographically representative datasets, the semantic landfill segmentation should grow, as the quality of training data and the diversity of these sets are critical factors in segmentation.

IX. IMPLEMENTATION

The source code for our project can be found in the following GitHub Repository: <https://github.com/Rakhmonberdiyev/Landfill-Detection-and-Semantic-Segmentation-from-Satellite-Imagery.git>

X. CONTRIBUTIONS

Amina Kenes - Project administration, Writing, Resources
Alikhan Zhumabayev - Software, Visualization, Data Curation
Daulet Zhailau - Software, Visualization, Resources
Raximberdi Raxmonberdiyev - Software, Methodology
Bagdat Zhubatkanov - Resources, Investigation

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